

HUMAN RIGHTS AS SECURITY ISSUE: THE CASE OF GREECE

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Abstract

The paper contributes to securitization theory by using its core concepts to argue that human rights of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in Greece are securitized. It analyses the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece finding a violation of the right to freedom of association of Macedonians through the prism of securitization theory. And, based on this qualitative content analysis, it explains that Greece perceives and treats the associations of ethnic Macedonians in the country as a security issue. The measures against the associations, described by the Strasbourg Court as not necessary in a democratic society, are taken by the Greek authorities (as extraordinary measures) in response to the alleged threat to state and nation (national identity) coming from the association. By presenting the arguments advanced by the authorities to justify the interference with the right to freedom of association the paper provides a starting point for future research on how to desecuritize the issue.

Key words: securitization, human rights, Greece, Macedonians, right to freedom of association

1. INTRODUCTION

The paper stems out from the research project “Macedonian minority in Greece and Bulgaria and Council of Europe” designed at the Faculty of Security – Skopje and conducted in the period 2022–2024. The starting point of the research project was the significant body of literature that criticizes both Greece and Bulgaria for human rights violations against the members of the Macedonian minority, referring to the human rights mechanisms established within the Council of Europe (see, for instance: Stojkov, 2021; Daskalovski, 2002; Ringelheim, 2002; de Varennes, 2004; Anagnostou & Psychogiopoulou, 2010; Grigoriadis, 2008; Kyriakou, 2009; Ibraimi, 2013; Tacev, 2011; Triandafyllidou & Kokkali, 2010; Baltiotis & Embrikos, 2001). The research attempts to explain the causes of these violations using securitization theory. The initial findings from the research have already been published (Milenkovska & Gerasimoski, 2024: 13-22). This paper particularly discusses the securitization of human rights of Macedonians living in Greece.

Securitization theory has been discussed in the literature on security extensively. In spite of certain critiques regarding its theoretical coherence, its methodology or its

normative and critical status, many issues, such as religion, health, migration, energy, environment, etc., have been studied through the prism of securitization theory (Baele & Thomson, 2022; Balzacq & Leonard, 2016, Nasu, 2021; Nyman, 2013; Vuković, 2022; Balzacq, 2018; Славески, 2010; Charrett, 2009; Jutila, 2006; Buzan, et al. 1998; Waever, 1995). As a new analytical framework, the theory has been used in many ways, but mainly to describe the process of securitization. This paper applies it to explain that certain measures (violations of the right to freedom of association of ethnic Macedonians in Greece) are consequences of agreeing that something is a threat (Macedonian minority), and, on that grounds, tries to understand how the securitization process works regarding this issue.

To support the thesis that the rights of ethnic Macedonians in Greece are being securitized, the paper applies qualitative content analysis of the three judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece, finding a violation of the rights of Macedonians. It analyses the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights available in the list of all judgments delivered by a Grand Chamber or Chamber, all advisory opinions and any related decisions as well as all decisions in key cases (Case-law references of judgments, advisory opinions and key case decisions) as updated until 25 November 2022).⁸ In other words, it analyses the following judgments: Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, from 1998; Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece, from 2005; and House of Macedonian Civilisation v. Greece, from 2015. The paper analyses these documents through the lenses of securitization theory.

Part I of the paper gives a short overview of the main concepts in the securitization theory. Using these concepts Part II of the paper provides arguments that the right to freedom of association of ethnic Macedonians in Greece is being securitized. The most salient findings of the paper, which contribute to securitization theory, are summarized in the conclusions.

2. SHORT ACCOUNT OF SECURITIZATION THEORY

Securitization theory⁹ is “conceptual framework explaining the process through which certain issues come to be perceived and treated as security threats” (Baele & Thomson, 2022, p. 174) to a designated referent object and “subsequently treated as an urgent matter to be dealt with outside normal political parameters” (Baele & Thomson, 2022, p. 184). Besides providing a constructivist operational method (Buzan et al. 1998; Nyman, 2013) “for understanding who can securitize what and under what conditions” (Buzan et al. 1998, p. vii), it embraced a wider security agenda (open to different types of threats) – introduced five security sectors (military, political, economic, environmental and societal) and thus “allowed recognition of new referent objects of security beyond the state” (Nyman, 2013, p. 56), such as nation and global market.

Securitization theory originates from the University of Copenhagen, and it’s been known as the Copenhagen school of security studies. However, its roots can be traced back to sociological constructivist theories inspired by the book “*The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*” (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Also, as it uses the terminology characteristic of interactionist approach (such as actors, public etc.), the securitization theory is said to have drawn its roots from interactionist theory in sociology as well, in specific, from the so called dramaturgical interactionist approach in

⁸. Downloaded from the official web site of the Council of Europe

⁹ For the main concepts of securitization theory see also: Milenkovska & Gerasimoski, 2024.

the sociological theory developed by Irwin Goffman (Goffman, 1956; Тамева, 1999: 388-394). Later on, on the foundations of sociological constructivist approach in sociology, a group of social and cultural constructivist theories within the risk theories developed, which argue that the security risk is a result of social and cultural construction (Douglas, 1992; Douglas & Wildavsky, 1982). According to this group of risk theories the word construction has the meaning of creation, more precisely socio-cultural creation, creation through socio-cultural relations, not of invention. By the same token, any social and cultural issue can be constructed as security issue under certain circumstances. If the participants in a socio-cultural relation view, perceive and assess an issue as a security issue for them, it can be considered a security issue, such as threat or risk, justifying any further action of dealing with it. Unlike the socio-cultural sphere, which does this informally, securitization theory does the same formally, i.e., in the sphere of security policy.

According to the founders of securitization theory, Barry Buzan, Jaap de Wilde and Ole Weaver, (explained in their book “Security: A New Framework for Analysis”), “the exact definition and criteria of securitization is constituted by the intersubjective establishment of an existential threat with a saliency sufficient to have substantial political effects” (Buzan et al. 1998, p. 25). We have a case of securitization “when a securitizing actor uses a rhetoric of existential threat and thereby takes an issue out of what under those conditions is “normal politics” (Buzan et al. 1998, p.24–25). By shifting an issue from the political to the security realm through intersubjective process, the actor (e.g. government) claims a right to take extraordinary measures (e.g. to place limitation on inviolable rights). It does not necessarily mean that a threat objectively exists. The issue is presented as security issue justifying action beyond normal politics through speech act. The Copenhagen school focuses on speech act, but securitization theory has broadened since its first formulation at the University of Copenhagen, “integrating linguistic processes beyond speech acts as well as non-linguistic factors (such as images and practices) and emotional dynamics” (Baele & Thomson, 2022, p. 179). In any case securitization depends on audience assent (acceptance). If the audience does not accept that something is a threat one cannot talk of successful securitization (of securitized issue), but only of securitizing move, that is of presenting an issue as an existential threat to designated referent object (Buzan et al. 1998; Balzacq and al. 2016; Stepka, 2022). Due to the fact that securitization is intersubjective, it’s much easier to securitize an issue than to desecuritize it. The process of construction or deconstruction of security issues consist of subjective and objective aspects, with the subjective aspect dominating at the beginning, while objective aspect arising as the securitization process develops. In fact, the securitization process becomes objectified thanks to intersubjectivity.

The analysis provided below does not discuss the process of construction or deconstruction of security issues, but, rather, it contributes to the literature on securitization theory by applying the theory to explain that certain measures (human rights violations) are consequences of agreeing that something is a threat. It explains that the rights of ethnic Macedonians in Greece are being securitized using the original conceptual apparatus of the securitization theory: the securitization actor (in this case, the Greek state (authorities)), existential threat (in our case, Macedonian national minority living in Greece), referent object of threat (in this case, state as object of threat and national identity as object of threat) and undertaken extraordinary measures (in this specific case, restriction of freedom of association).

3. SECURITIZATION OF THE RIGHT TO FREEDOM OF ASSOCIATION: THE CASE OF THE MACEDONIAN MINORITY IN GREECE

The analysis of the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece finding a violation of the right to freedom of association of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in the country (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece*, 1998; *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece*, 2005; and *House of Macedonian Civilisation v. Greece*, 2015) shows that the modern Greek state finds it adequate and justifiable to securitize the basic human rights of the Macedonian minority living mainly in their northern part. Acting as securitizing actor from the viewpoint of a typical nation-state, it perceives and treats the issue of the basic human rights of the Macedonian minority as a political and security one, and, on that grounds, justifies the implementation of extraordinary security, legal and political measures to what it deems to be a security risk, threat or danger to their values. The ECtHR's judgments clearly support the position that Greece is trying to base and justify their measures against the associations of ethnic Macedonians by referring to the alleged threat, or risk, to their national and cultural integrity, security and public order, thus, in fact securitizing the threat or risk, more precisely. It is important to note that most of the mentions that prove the securitization thesis found in these three judgments were direct, detailed, explicit and unambiguous and they contributed towards the verification of the securitization thesis.

The judgment of the ECHR *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece* case from 2005, represents a peculiar example of violation of human rights of Macedonians living in Greece, in terms of violation of the right of their freedom of association. Ouranio Toxo, which means Rainbow in English and Vinožito in Macedonian, is the name of the only political party of the persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in Greece. The detailed qualitative content analysis of the ECHR *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece* case from 2005, has shown clear securitization of the right of freedom of association of Macedonian minority, which was done by Greek state and Greek authorities in general, as securitization actor. We'll mention only one out of six instances within this ECHR judgment, which clearly and indisputably confirm the securitization of Macedonian minority human right to freedom of association.

An excerpt from the ECHR *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece* case from 2005, states that “in the present case, the Court notes that the Ouranio Toxo party is a legally established party, one of whose aims is the defence of the Macedonian minority living in Greece. The placing of a sign on the front of the headquarters with the party's name written in Macedonian cannot be considered as condemnatory or as constituting in itself a present and imminent threat to public order. The Court accepts that the use of the term Vinožito certainly aroused hostile feelings among the local population. Its ambiguous connotations could offend the political or patriotic views of the majority of the population of Florina [the Macedonian form Lerin]. However, the risk of provoking tensions in the community by the use of political terms in public is not sufficient, in itself, to justify an interference with freedom of association” (*Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece*, para. 41). This clearly indicates that Greek state securitizes the right to freedom of association of Macedonians. Moreover, it actually securitizes not only the alleged and perceived threat, but, which is more interesting, it securitizes the risk. And while the reference to threat points out to some imminent danger, the reference to risk aims to indicate that, according to the Greek authorities, even when there is no real danger in the form of a threat, there is still a risk as a possibility that in a longer process it could become a threat to the values of the Greek state (in this case, public order).

The analysis of the other two cases under discussion in this paper, which concern the refusal of the Greek authorities to register a non-profit making association (House of Macedonian Civilization) asserting the Macedonian national consciousness, also supports the position that the Greek authorities treat the associations of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority living in Greece as a security issue. The aims of the association were: “(a) the cultural, intellectual and artistic development of its members and of the inhabitants of Florina in general and the fostering of a spirit of cooperation, solidarity and love between them; (b) cultural decentralisation and the preservation of intellectual and artistic endeavours and traditions and of the civilisation’s monuments and, more generally, the promotion and development of [their] folk culture; and (c) the protection of the region’s natural and cultural environment” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.8.*) Although such aims were assessed by the ECtHR as perfectly clear and legitimate, it has not been registered yet.

As the Court’s judgment in the case *Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece* (which concerns the initial rejection of the application for registration) reveals the national authorities in order to justify the interference with the right to freedom of association referred to “the maintenance of national security, the prevention of disorder and the upholding of Greece’s cultural traditions and historical and cultural symbols” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.37.*) The Government defended the position of the domestic courts that the name of the organisation could cause confusion in the country and they had “good reasons ... to believe that the purpose of using the term ‘Macedonian’ [was] to dispute the Greek identity of Macedonia and its inhabitants by indirect and therefore underhand means, and discern[ed] in it an intention on the part of the founders to undermine Greece’s territorial integrity (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece , para. 44.*) However, the ECtHR did not accept that the association represents a danger to Greek identity and Greece’s territorial integrity. According to the Court “the inhabitants of a region in a country are entitled to form associations in order to promote the region’s special characteristics, for historical as well as economic reasons” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.44.*) And, as it explained “even supposing that the founders of an association like the one in the instant case assert a minority consciousness, the Document of the Copenhagen Meeting of the Conference on the Human Dimension of the CSCE (Section IV) of 29 June 1990 and the Charter of Paris for a New Europe of 21 November 1990 – which Greece has signed – allow them to form associations to protect their cultural and spiritual heritage” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.44.*)

The ECtHR reiterated the same position in the case of *House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece*, emphasizing that the refusal to register the applicants’ association – “on the basis of more or less the same line of reasoning as that adopted by them in the *Sidiropoulos and Others* case” (*House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece, para. 38*) – was disproportionate to the objectives pursued (public safety and protection of public order). The Greek authorities again failed to convince the Court that the use of the term Macedonian – which according to the domestic courts in its historical sense was part of Greek civilization because “there was no Macedonian civilization or language” (*House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece, para. 38*) – in the name of the association could cause confusion within the country regarding the identity of the association and disturb the public order” (*House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece, para. 38*) .

The measures taken by the Greek authorities against the association asserting the Macedonian national consciousness named House of Macedonian Civilization (like the measures against the political party Rainbow (Vinožito)) did not pass the test of the

European Court of Human Rights of being necessary in a democratic society, so one can consider them as extraordinary, and argue that by interfering with the right to freedom of association in a manner which amounts to human rights violations, Greece breaks the normal political rules of the game within the meaning explained by the founders of the securitization theory (see Buzan et al. 1998).

As the analysis of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights provided above shows the Greek authorities claimed a need for the interventions against the associations by referring to the alleged existential threat to certain referent object (Greek state and national identity (nation)) coming from them. The Greek state constructs the human rights as security issue, thereby trying to justify the usage of extraordinary political, legal and security measures against the members of Macedonian national minority in Greece. It takes out the issue of human rights, which normally belongs in the societal and cultural sphere, and constructs it as a security one. It is evident that the Greek authorities securitize not only what they consider to be real threat, but, moreover, they securitize the risk, the potentiality of future threat or endangerment. At the same time, this is the argument advanced in the ECtHR's judgments, which criticize Greece for violation and not respecting the right to freedom of association of Macedonian national minority, for, according to the law, no legal authority can restrict or deny any human right on the basis of assumed risk or threat, but only on their actual deeds undertaken in reality and in present time. Risk and threat are mere security assumptions and if not sustained by real acts of undermining or threatening the core values of state or society, cannot be considered as sufficient, justifiable and necessary reasons for securitization.

4. CONCLUSION

The paper puts forward that the rights of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in Greece are being securitized, by referring to data collected within the research project "Macedonian minority in Greece and Bulgaria and Council of Europe" designed at the Faculty of Security – Skopje. More precisely, it referred to the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece collected within the research. The paper provided sound arguments that Greek authorities perceive and treat the Macedonian minority as source of threat to different referent objects (state and national identity) by analysing the judgments through the lens of securitization theory. The analysis showed that interventions against the associations asserting the Macedonian national consciousness in Greece (which did not pass the ECtHR's test of being necessary in a democratic society) are taken (as extraordinary measures) by the authorities (securitizing actor) in response to the alleged existential threat to state and/or nation (referent objects) coming from them. Greece takes out the issue of human rights, which normally belongs in societal and cultural sphere, and constructs it as a security one. Moreover, based on the analysis provided in this paper, one may argue that Greece securitizes not only what it considers to be real threat, but, also the risk, the potentiality of future threat or endangerment. This thesis deserves to be thoroughly and extensively researched and elaborated in the future.

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